

TECHNOLOGY FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF SPEECH SKILLS IN EIGHTH GRADE STUDENTS IN THE PROCESS OF STUDYING THE HISTORY OF UZBEKISTAN

Botirova Sevara Ma'murovna

NamSU researcher

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7445279>

Annotation: This article discusses the conditions for the successful development of speech and communication skills in eighth grade students, as well as the process of studying the subject of the history of Uzbekistan. The technology of developing speech skills, we show that the process is long and complex. The development of speech skills is closely related to critical thinking and is the basis for the perception of a particular historical event.

Key words: technology, significant, history, process, communication, perform, transfers, world history

Today we can observe how significant changes are taking place in schools, covering almost all aspects of the pedagogical process. The personal interest of the student is the main factor in the success of the educational process. Interest in the lesson arises when three conditions are met: the creative personality of the teacher, the interesting content of the educational material, the use of modern pedagogical technologies. The search for new ways of training and education aimed at developing the personality of the student, at creating conditions conducive to facilitating the process of their social adaptation, is becoming increasingly important. The history teacher must perform a deeper task than just a transmitter of data and information to the younger generation. Its functions include the development of schoolchildren's worldview ideals, their worldview, and civic position. "Over the years of independence, large-scale work has been carried out and is continuously ongoing to restore the ancient history and rich culture of our people, to comprehensively in-depth research and popularize the scientific, religious and spiritual heritage of great scientists, to improve places of sacred worship, to educate the youth of a generation in accordance with their good traditional spirit. ...[1].

The state policy in the field of historical education is based on the principles of a scientific approach, preserving the originality and depth of historical knowledge, its "wide promotion in the world community, effective use in the development of modern science, spirituality and practice, transfers the works of our great scientists and thinkers to the next generation" [1].

In history lessons, we constantly use the following technologies for the development of critical thinking, which contribute to the development of

students' speech skills. The subject of history is associated with a huge number of names, dates and historical events. Schoolchildren are also afraid to make a mistake, forget the name or date. Of course, such a subject as the history of Uzbekistan cannot exist without dates, events and heroic personalities. One of the most important moments in the assimilation of historical material is its adaptation by the student to a precisely defined, special time.

A prerequisite for history lessons: the use of specific historical dates, events and heroic personalities in stories. You can also ask students to put themselves in the place of famous historical characters and think about options for important decisions that influenced the course of world history. The method teaches you to fully immerse yourself in certain historical periods, perceive this or that heroic personality, understand the cause-and-effect relationships. The main task of the modern school is the formation of a linguistic personality capable of adapting to various social conditions, possessing a high culture and developed communication skills. In this regard, the developing role of speech skills and the formation of a communicative culture and cognitive interests of students is increasing. Developed speech is considered as a valuable material of oneself, and the development of speech becomes the central task of personality development. This important task should be solved not only in the lessons of the Russian language and literature, but also in the lessons of history.

As a result of studying history, the student must first of all be able to: formulate his own position on the questions asked, use historical information to argue it; to formulate their worldview views and principles, correlating them with historically emerged worldview systems; compare and analyze historical events and phenomena.

Fiction and historical literature is an important source of familiarization of students with the historical past. Artistic images facilitate the perception of the historical past and increase the visibility of the presentation of the material; the emotional impact of the teacher's story in the history lesson contributes not only to the formation of ideas about the past, but also helps to remember the material for a long time; comparing descriptions of the same events in fiction and historical writing contributes to the development of students' critical thinking. Fiction and historical literature used in the teaching of history is divided into two groups of works. The first includes literary sources of the period under study, the second - historical fiction.

At the same time, historical novels can be actively used as a means of teaching children about history, as they increase motivation and acquaint them with the

results of historical research. Moreover, this format is becoming more accessible to the widest range of students. This form of presentation of the material is more figurative and expressive. The study of history in this format becomes exciting and interesting [2].

It is useful for the teacher, when preparing for the lesson, to include in the plan of his story separate small passages, brief descriptions, vivid descriptions of historical events, and this can equally serve as material for the development of speech skills in schoolchildren. This definition as "cognitive activity" is closely related to the process of research and analysis of literary texts in the process of studying the history of Uzbekistan. Thus, the teacher must identify the following types of historical text that can be used in the school process: memoirs, historical literary works, fiction written by contemporaries of a bygone era.

The teacher should be able to conduct an oral dialogue with students: ask questions to the student, build answers to questions, freely conduct a conversation. The development of speech skills in students is facilitated by such types of educational activities as role-playing or business games. Educational discussion is also one of the methods that help the teacher to form a competent, reasoned speech of schoolchildren. The meaning of this method is to exchange views on a specific problem. Through discussion, students acquire new knowledge, exchange views, strengthen their own opinions, and learn to defend them.

In the lessons on the history of Uzbekistan, it is also possible to conduct "debates", as a formalized discussion, built on the basis of pre-fixed performances of students - two opposing, rival teams. The development of monologue speech: to give a detailed answer to a question, to make a verbal description of an event, a historical person, a discussion on a given topic, a speech with an oral message, a report, a presentation of project work, an excursion in a museum, etc. [3]. . It is very useful at the initial stage of studying history to teach the retelling of a historical text. This contributes to the development of memory, develops and forms speech skills and correct speech.

Work on coherent oral speech includes "drawing" a verbal picture using pictures or situational pictures, making sentences, a story. The use of logical diagrams and tables that help to systematize and classify historical material. A story based on an illustration especially helps students to make a sentence about one or another historical character, describe his feat, selfless work, etc.

Teaching retelling is a means of developing speech skills in schoolchildren. Students must read the text, pick up historical words, modern expressions, be

able to retell the text in detail. An important means of forming the communicative competence of students is the vocabulary of words. Vocabulary work contributes to learning how to take notes on the text, write an answer plan or an article, essay, composition, compiling memos, filling out tables, etc. Enriches students' vocabulary (working with concepts, historicisms, catch-phrases).

Vocabulary work is a close learning process in teaching history (it is correct to use historical terms not only during the answer in the lesson, but also to use new words in everyday speech). It is important to draw students' attention to the need for literate speech and correct mistakes in a timely manner, to show the brightness of our language [4].

The student, so that he does not read from a piece of paper, but easily remembers the text of the speech, he must think over the general plan of the speech. His speech must be intelligible, competent and correct, then it will be understandable to the listener. He must speak truthfully and sincerely, not violating the generally accepted norms of behavior and morality. In the process of communication, it is necessary to observe a culture of listening.

References:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-2995 dated May 24, 2017 "On measures to further improve the system of storage, research and promotion of ancient written sources."
2. Vagin A.A. Fiction in the teaching of modern history (1640–1917). Reader for the teacher. - M.: Education, 1966. - S. 43-45.
3. Vyazemsky E.E., Strelova O.Yu. Methods of teaching history at school: a practical guide. M., 2000.
4. Sharmanova T. V. The development of speech in history lessons // Teaching history at school. - No. 10. - 2011.
5. Nodirbek Kodirov Mamasoliyevich. (2021). CURRENT ISSUES OF FORMATION OF INFORMATION CULTURE IN YOUTH. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5770626>

